

D3.2 – DigiMedFor Data Traceability Platform System

DIGIMEDFOR

Digital tools and technology systems for the sustainable
management of Mediterranean forest resources

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
DTPS	Data Traceability Platform System
EUDR	European Union Regulation on Deforestation-free Products
EUTR	EU Timber Regulation
FMU	Forest Management Unit
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GU	Guest User
HM220	HitMan 220
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
OSNMA	Open Service Navigation Message Authentication
PEFC	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
SA	Super Admin
SU	Super User
U	User
UAS	Unmanned Aerial System

Executive Summary

The DigiMedFor Data Traceability Platform System (DTPS) represents a comprehensive digital solution for the traceability and quality assurance of Mediterranean forest resources, supporting sustainable forest management and regulatory compliance. Developed within the DigiMedFor project, the DTPS integrates advanced digital tools-including a web-based Gateway, a mobile Android application, and a drone-mounted Traceability Box-to enable end-to-end tracking of timber and wood products from standing trees through to processed sawn timber.

The DTPS is designed to address the needs of a diverse user base, including forest managers, logging companies, sawmills, drone operators, auditors, and downstream buyers. It supports multiple use cases reflecting real-world timber supply chain scenarios, such as single-operator management, multi-actor chains involving sawmills, and cases where forest ownership and management are distinct.

Central to the system is the coupling of physical wood elements (trees, logs, sawn timber) with RFID tags, ensuring each item's unique identification and traceability. The platform captures a wide range of data, including administrative, qualitative, and quantitative attributes, as well as compliance evidence for no-deforestation requirements, supported by authenticated drone survey data and blockchain-backed data integrity.

Key components include:

- **Gateway (Web Platform):** The main user interface for registration, data management, visualization, and generation of traceability reports, interfaced with a blockchain service for immutable record-keeping.
- **Android App:** Enables field data collection and RFID tagging, supporting workflows for adding and measuring trees, logs, and sawn timber, as well as managing loads and batches for transport and processing.
- **Traceability Box (UAS Module):** A lightweight, drone-mounted device that securely records and transmits geolocated flight data, providing verifiable evidence of forest conditions and harvesting activities.

The DTPS supports a hierarchical user structure with tailored access and functionalities to match operational roles and regulatory responsibilities, particularly in alignment with EU regulations such as the EUDR.

Traceability reports generated by the system consolidate both timber production data and certified drone flight trajectories, each linked to blockchain records and accessible via QR codes. This ensures transparency and facilitates audits by customers and regulatory authorities.

This deliverable (D3.2) provides a detailed user manual for the first prototype of the DTPS, outlining its architecture, functionalities, and operational workflows. It is linked to other DigiMedFor project deliverables and will be updated in subsequent versions based on pilot feedback and evolving regulatory standards. The platform is positioned as a key enabler for digital transformation in Mediterranean forestry, fostering traceability, quality assurance, and legal compliance throughout the timber value chain.

1. Introduction

1.1. Aims of the deliverable

This Deliverable aims to provide a description of the first version of the prototype of the DIGIMEDFOR Data Traceability Platform System.

D3.2 is structured as a User Manual of the Data Traceability Platform System (DTPS), thus describing the features and workflows to the intended potential users in a practical approach.

After Section 1 (Introduction), the following sections are:

- Section 2: “Data Traceability System Overview” introduces the system, together with the description of the addressed use cases, users, and traceability, quality and no-deforestation information
- Section 3: “Gateway and Blockchain” presents the web platform and the features based on the blockchain technology, including the generation of the Traceability Report.
- Section 4 “Android App” describes the mobile app for on-field data acquisition.
- Section 5 “UAS Module – Traceability Box” describes the traceability device with its respective instructions.
- Section 6 “Final remarks” outlines future developments currently identified for the definitive version of the system (D3.6).
- Section 7, titled "References," enumerates the sources and documents cited within the Deliverable.
- Appendix 1 “Report Template”: an example of the Traceability Report.

Reading note: When referring to the DTPS as a whole, the term "System" will also be used. The term "Platform" alone is a synonym for the Gateway module.

1.2. Relevance for Targeted Stakeholders

This document addresses the potential users and adopters of the DTPS, in particular Forest managers and workers, Sawmill managers and workers and drone professionals. DTPS fosters the digitalization of the traceability information, together with timber quality information, and produces a Traceability Report in support of the documentation needed for the Due Diligence, and the simplified Due Diligence in Countries with low deforestation risk, as per the EUDR and its implementations measures.

Other intended readers are Auditors of different types: experts of EUTR and EUDR, experts of Certification schemes like FSC and PEFC, officials who issue logging permits and oversee forestry operations.

The document is hopefully also of interest to final users such as buyers downstream of the wood traceability chain.

1.3. Relation with other deliverables

This Deliverable is linked to others of the DigiMedFor Project, some preparatory, such as D2.1, D2.2, and D6.6, other siblings such as D3.1, to which it is closely linked due to the synergy with which the issues of wood quality and traceability are treated, and finally others that may address the refinement and modifications to be included in D3.6 (final version of D3.2), such as D6.7.

In summary, the DigiMedFor deliverables in relation to D3.2 are:

- Preparatory:
 - D2.1 - Report on DigiMedFor forest data: used as input for Forest Units Attributes design.
 - D2.2 - Toolkit for Forest Managers.
 - D6.6 - Regulatory framework.
- Siblings
 - D3.1 - DigiMedFor tool for in-situ wood evaluation and grading.
- Successive
 - D6.7 - Recommendations on compliance and adaptation of standards.

2. Data Traceability Platform System Overview

2.1. Architecture presentation

This document describes the modules and features of the Data Traceability Platform System.

The following Figure 1 shows a high-level architecture, which highlights the main modules further described in the document, in particular:

- **Gateway:** the module collects data about the forest units from three sources:
 - Forest Manager, entering administrative and inventory data,
 - Android App,
 - Traceability Box,and is integrated with the Blockchain service to immutably record the collected data. The Gateway is also the main user interface for registration, data visualization, and generation of traceability report.
- **Mobile App:** this module feeds the Gateway with data collected “on ground” with two types of sub-systems:
 - RFID Reader: this device, bound with a tablet or a smartphone, reads the RFID tags attached to physical elements (standing trees, wood logs, ...)
 - HM220: this device provides measurements used for wood quality evaluation.
- **Traceability Box:** this device is a tracker installed on drones performing surveys of the Forest Unit(s) to provide data (such as orthomosaic, or LIDAR 3D point clouds) and reports addressing the “proof-of-no-deforestation”. This “Box” ensures position authenticity by leveraging a specific European-GNSS service, thus ensuring the reliability of the data generated by the drone survey.
- **Blockchain database:** this module is interfaced with the Gateway, synchronizing traceability data in an unalterable register, this module is not directly accessible to Users, who can simply generate the Traceability Report and visualize excerpts of the blockchain register.

Figure 1

The document contains graphic symbols to indicate suggestions, hazards, or damage to the equipment or its components. They are used as follows:

This symbol indicates that the box contains suggestions and clarifying information.

This symbol indicates valuable information that the user must follow for the device to function properly.

2.2. Key information

2.2.1. Use cases

This System addresses the digitalization of wood traceability and quality information, focusing on the perspective of Forest Managers in the context of Mediterranean Forests.

USE CASE "A" - Baseline

The main use case considers the presence of a single subject, controlling the very initial steps of timber supply chain, from the standing trees to the harvesting, logging and stockpiling, to the first processing in the sawmill and the consequent sale to third parties.

In this baseline use case, the Forest Manager coincides with the "Operator" who, according to the definitions of the EUDR [art.2]¹, is: *"any natural or legal person who, in the course of a commercial activity, places relevant products on the market or exports them"*.

Other use cases are:

- USE CASE "B"
 - B1. In this case the Forest Manager is still the "Operator", but its client is the same Sawmill, which is a different subject. The Forest Manager is only interested in the traceability from the Forest Unit to the wood logs and the Load of Logs. Once generated the Traceability Report and sold the Load of Logs to the Sawmill, the Forest Manager will provide the Sawmill with access as "guest user" the system.
 - B2. The Sawmill Manager intends to implement the DTPS for the wood processing activities. The Sawmill Manager will need to create a new subscription to the service as an SU. To create the Forest Unit, the system requires the Sawmill Manager to enter the information available in the Traceability Report. In this way, the System will synchronize the information of the purchased Load of Logs with the FMU of origin, ensuring the consistency of the Traceability System.
- USE CASE "C"

The forest owner is a different subject with respect to the logging company: for example, the owner sells the trees "standing" to another subject who cuts them and places them on the market. As in the baseline case, the Logging company is the "Operator" according to the EUDR.

To learn more about the obligations of the Operators established by the EUDR read this [article](#).

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02023R1115-20241226>

2.2.2. Types of Users

These types of users are classified according to their “role” and responsibilities in the Data Traceability Platform System.

Role	Description	Access policy	“EUDR” Role
SuperAdmin (SA)	Is the “service provider” of the DTPS, manages the entire platform	Full access, including back-end, for platform management and maintenance	n/a
Super User (SU)	Is the owner or the Forest Manager, the Sawmill Manager, or the Logging Company manager. Is the subscriber.	Complete access to the account and its features, including management of subordinate users	Operator
User (U)	User level subordinate to the Super User. Is a Forest worker, or a Logging Company Worker, a Sawmill worker, or a subcontractor (i.e. drone operator)	Access limited to assigned Forest Management Unit(s), and or to assigned Batches of wood logs or sawn timber. Limited authorization to data entry / editing / upload	Belongs to the “Super User” organization
Guest User (GU)	User level subordinate to the SU and U levels. Is a third-party like: - client, - auditor	Only visualization, limited to assigned Forest Management Unit, or sawn timber batches	Is a “trader” or a “competent authority”

Table 1

2.2.3. Access Levels

Super User - SU

After the first registration and access, the System automatically assigns the “Super User” (SU) Access Level.

SU accesses all functionalities in the Account:

- Account management (subscription, credentials)
- Create and edit Forest Management Unit (FMU)
- Uploading files to the FMU (i.e.: json, Harvesting Authorization, Drone Survey Report)
- Access to the Android App and related data entries (including RFID tags reader and HM220 measurements)
- Generation of Traceability Report

- Invite other members:
 - Users,
 - Guest Users.

SU can invite other members from the same Organization, or subcontractors like Aerial Service Providers, which will be assigned as Users (U), with limited access.

SU can finally invite members from third parties, namely:

- Customers,
- Auditors.

User (U)

The User accesses the platform at the invitation of the SU.

The platform will classify all users associated with the SU account as "U".

The U can only operate on the FMUs created by the SU and cannot create new FMUs.

U can:

- Edit some FMU attributes
- Uploading files to the FMU (i.e.: json, Drone Survey Report)
- Access to the Android App and related data entries (including RFID tags reader and HM220 measurements).

"U" cannot generate the Traceability Report.

Guest User (GU)

GU can only visualize the traceability information of interest with respect to the Traceability Report that has been shared with them.

GU only visualizes the Forest Unit Information, as described in §3.4.5.

2.2.4. Types of information

Traceability information assumes the coupling of the physical objects to RFID tags to associate their unique id to their respective information.

Traceability information is associated with different Traceability Elements. A Traceability Element is a logic entity describing one of the “items” in the different steps of the traceability chain. These elements are:

- Forest Management Unit
- Tree
- Wood Log
- Load of Logs
- Sawn Timber
- Batch of Sawn Timber

Together with the Traceability information, it is also possible to add **Quality information** to classify the timber production according to the objectives of the Operator.

This information is:

- Qualitative attributes of the Forest Management Unit
- Diameter (1 and 2) of Wood logs
- “Stiffness” of Wood Logs
- Dimensions (Width, Length, and Thickness), and quality grade of Sawn Timber

The Data Traceability Platform System also allows users to support their **no-deforestation** compliance with third parties (e.g. competent authorities). In fact, if drone surveys are carried out at the beginning and at the end of the harvesting period (provided for by the Harvesting permit), the use of the Traceability Box [§ 5] allows to demonstrate the execution of these measurements in the period and in the location of interest.

Following the recent classification by the European Commission based on EUDR risk², all Mediterranean countries (except Israel) and most of the world's countries, are considered "low risk".

This means that wood and other raw materials regulated by the EUDR and produced in these states will not require special investigations related to deforestation when they are placed on the European Union market. *

The traceability of supply chains also remains a prerequisite for the so-called "simplified due diligence" applicable to low-risk countries. .

The following Table 2 describes, for each traceability element, the corresponding information either collected in the Platform and in the Android App, according to this legenda:

- Traceability information: No color
- Qualitative information: Light green
- No-deforestation information: Light blue

² https://green-forum.ec.europa.eu/deforestation-regulation-implementation/eudr-cooperation-and-partnerships/country-classification-list_en

Traceability Element	Traceability /Quality /No deforestation information	How it is entered into the system	DTPS Module
Forest Management Unit	Administrative attributes	SU fills in the Create Forest Unit form	Gateway
	Qualitative attributes		
	Quantitative attributes		
	List of the "ID" s of the traceability elements associated to the FMU	Scanning RFID tags	Android App
	EUDR "Operator"	SU fills in the form when Generating the Traceability Report	Gateway
	Forest Management Unit shapefile (.kml; .json)	SU uploads the .kml or the .json	Gateway
	Authenticated Drone Trajectory (list of coordinates and timestamps)	The Traceability Box transmits the flight trajectory to the Gateway.	UAS Module - Gateway
Trees	Tree ID (unique ID of the RFID tag attached)	U attaches the RFID tag of the Tree and scans it	Android App
	EPC (unique ID of the individual element, can be modified by the User)		
	First reading time (timestamp of the RFID tag)		
	Coordinates of first RFID tags scan		
	Tree species		
	Forest Management Unit (ID)	Gateway-Android App synchronization	Gateway
	Wood Logs, and Load of Logs		Android App
	Sawn Timber, and Batches of Sawn Timber		
Wood Logs	Wood Log ID (unique ID of the RFID tag attached)	U attaches the RFID tag on the Wood Log and scans it	Android App
	EPC (unique ID of the individual element, can be modified by the User)		
	First Reading Time		
	Tree species		
	Log section number		
	Tree ID		
	Observations		
	- Diameter 1	U measures the value and enters it (Android app)	
	Time of Publication		
	- Diameter 2		

	<i>Time of Publication</i>		
	<i>Length</i>		
	<i>Time of publication</i>		
	<i>Velocity</i>	U measures the value with the HM220	
	<i>Time of Publication</i>		
Load of Logs	Load of Logs ID (unique ID code generated by the system)	The code is generated when the Load of Logs is created in the Android App.	Android App
	Name of the Load	U fills-in the field in the Android App (i.e. "Truck 1")	
	List of Wood Logs	U scans the RFID tags of the logs to be added to the Load	
	Number of Wood Logs	The App gives the number of scanned Wood Logs ID	
Sawn Timber	Sawn Timber ID (unique ID of the RFID tag attached)	U attaches the RFID tag onto the Sawn timber and scans it	Android App
	EPC (Editable ID of the individual element)		
	First reading time (timestamp of the RFID tag)		
	Tree species		
	<i>Observations:</i>	U measures the value and types it (Android app)	
	<i>Sawn Timber in this batch (quantity)</i>		
	<i>Time of Publication</i>		
	<i>Width of Sawn Timber</i>		
	<i>Time of Publication</i>		
	<i>Length of Sawn Timber</i>		
	<i>Time of Publication</i>		
	<i>Thickness of Sawn Timber</i>		
	<i>Time of Publication</i>		
	<i>Quality Category</i>		
<i>Time of Publication</i>			
Batch of Sawn Timber	Batch of Sawn Timber ID (unique ID of the RFID tag attached to the batch) It appears like the Sawn Timber, but has a quantity of Sawn Timber > 1	U attaches the RFID tag (or equivalent) on the Batch and scans it	Android App

Table 2

The FMU attributes are detailed in the §3.4.

3. Gateway and Blockchain

3.1. Description

The Gateway is the web interface for users of the System, aimed at the digitized management of information relating to the Forest Management Units and other elements subject to traceability.

The Gateway interfaces with the blockchain service to synchronize recorded information via smart contracts, allowing SU to generate a "Traceability Report" for Customers and Auditors.

The Gateway is accessible at this link: [DigiMedFor Data Traceability Platform System Gateway.](#)

3.2. Homepage

The Homepage briefly describes the DigiMedFor project. A link to the project website is provided in the page footer.

The screenshot shows the homepage of the DigiMedFor Data Traceability Platform System. The header is green with the DigiMedFor logo and navigation links: Home, Log in, and Sign up. The main content area is white with a green border. It features a welcome message, a project summary, and several key messages. The project summary is titled 'Project summary' and includes sections: 'Mediterranean Forests: A Precious Resource at Risk', 'DigiMedFor: Modernizing the Mediterranean Forest-Wood Supply Chain', 'Bridging Nature and Technology', 'Cutting-Edge Technologies for Sustainability', 'A Strong Consortium of Diverse Expertise', 'Real-World Testing Ground: The Mediterranean Model Forest Network', and 'Paving the Way for a Sustainable Future'. At the bottom, there is a section for 'DigiMedFor Knowledge Platform (DKP)'. The footer is green with the copyright notice: © 2025 DigiMedFor.

Welcome to DigiMedFor Data Traceability Platform System

Transforming Mediterranean Forestry through Digital Innovation

DigiMedFor is a pioneer in forestry and digital innovation, transforming Mediterranean forestry. We employ advanced technology, including geospatial analysis and artificial intelligence, to ensure a sustainable future for our forests and ecosystems.

Our vision: sustainability, innovation, and collaboration. Explore our website and join our community. DigiMedFor – where nature meets digital innovation.

Project summary

Mediterranean Forests: A Precious Resource at Risk

With over 25 million hectares of forests and approximately 50 million hectares of other wooded lands in the Mediterranean region, climate changes and socio-economic factors can have far-reaching consequences for forests and the forest-wood supply chain, potentially leading to the loss of vital ecosystem services. These changes pose challenges to forest managers and industries, mainly due to limited access to modern digital technologies that fail to address emergent industry needs and innovations expected in the coming decades.

DigiMedFor: Modernizing the Mediterranean Forest-Wood Supply Chain

This is the underlying objective of the DigiMedFor project, which aims to modernize the technological landscape of the Mediterranean forest-wood supply chain. The project simultaneously focuses on enhancing competitiveness and sustainable management by ensuring the traceability of wood resources from the forest to end-users.

Bridging Nature and Technology

Harnessing the current digital revolution, stakeholders can effectively manage Mediterranean forests and improve the provision of ecosystem services associated with them. DigiMedFor aligns with the forest strategy and digital strategy of the European Union, leveraging advanced and innovative digital solutions to enhance the monitoring and management of forest resources throughout the supply chain, from their origin in the forest to processing in the primary wood industry.

Cutting-Edge Technologies for Sustainability

The project integrates various technologies, including geospatial analysis, artificial intelligence (AI), and digital twin modeling technologies with information and communication technology (ICT) to improve the sustainability of wood production and optimize traceability and delivery of ecosystem services.

A Strong Consortium of Diverse Expertise

DigiMedFor's consortium comprises 21 beneficiaries from European and non-European countries, with diverse expertise covering the entire value chain from research to operations. The consortium includes representatives from the forest industry, forest owners, academic and research institutes, and SMEs.

Real-World Testing Ground: The Mediterranean Model Forest Network

The forests belonging to the Mediterranean Model Forest Network serve as case studies for demonstrating and applying the digital and technology solutions developed in the DigiMedFor project.

Paving the Way for a Sustainable Future

DigiMedFor aims to pave the way for a more competitive, sustainable, and technologically advanced forest-wood supply chain in the Mediterranean region by bringing together key stakeholders and leveraging digital innovations.

Coordinator: Department of Agricultural Sciences – University of Naples FEDERICO II

DigiMedFor Knowledge Platform (DKP)

As part of the DigiMedFor project wider framework, the Data Traceability Platform System is linked to the DigiMedFor Knowledge Platform (DKP); by clicking the link <https://dkp.cefor.org/it/>, it is possible to obtain desired optimal forest pathway, while also accessing to a complete repository of forestry datasets and investigation.

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Figure 2

3.3. Users

3.3.1. New User registration

From the Homepage, to register as a new user, click on "Sign up" in the top menu (Figure 3) and fill-in the required fields to Create a new DigiMedFor Account.

Create a new DigiMedFor Account

First name

Last name

Username*

Required. 150 characters or fewer. Letters, digits and @/./+/-/_ only.

Email*

A valid email address, please.

Password*

- Your password can't be too similar to your other personal information.
- Your password must contain at least 8 characters.
- Your password can't be a commonly used password.
- Your password can't be entirely numeric.

Password confirmation*

Enter the same password as before, for verification.

I have received a report with a Load of Logs ID

[Sign Up](#)

Already Have An Account? [Sign In](#)

Figure 3

If the SU is a Sawmill Manager (Use Case B2, check §2.2.1), is possible to enter the unique ID of the Load of Logs (Figure 4) present in the Traceability Report to ensure the continuation of the traceability of wood and its subsequent processing as Sawn Timber.

I have received a report with a Load of Logs ID

Enter the Load of Logs ID contained inside the report

Sign Up

Figure 4

Registered Users can directly Log in using their Username (or email) and Password (Figure 5).

DigiMedFor - Digital Mediterranean Forest Home Log in Sign up

Log In to your DigiMedFor Account

Username or Email**
mario.rossi@email.it

Password*
.....

Captcha*
 Non sono un robot reCAPTCHA Privacy - Termini

Login

Need An Account? [Sign Up Now](#)
[Forgot password?](#)

Figure 5

Once logged in, the User visualizes the complete Top Menu as in figure below.

DigiMedFor - Digital Mediterranean Forest Home UserName Forest Units Map Devices Accounts Management Log out

Hello **UserName!** You have been logged in

Welcome to DigiMedFor Data Traceability Platform System

Figure 6

3.3.2. User Profiling

Each user can modify information provided during registration.

DigiMedFor - Digital Mediterranean Forest Home **UserName** Forest Units Map Devices Accounts Management Log out

Profile Information:

 UserName (Super User)
Mario Rossi

Edit Profile Information

First name

Last name

Email*

Phone

Company

Country

[Change password?](#)

Figure 7

3.3.3. Accounts Management

This section is available from the top Menu only for the SU.

Figure 8

Here, the SU can:

- Invite Users, as shown in Figure 9,
- Manage Users' access level (User or Guest User), as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9

Accounts Management			
Username	Email	Current Role	Change Role
GuestUser01	ascione.vincenzomaria@gmail.com	Guest User	Guest User <input type="button" value="Update"/>
VincenzoAscioneTopView	vincenzo.ascione@topview.it	User	User <input type="button" value="Update"/>

Figure 10

3.3.4. Invited Users

Invited Users receive an email as in Figure 11. They have to click the link in the e-mail to register, then follow the steps described in § 3.3.1

Figure 11

Then, they will receive a mail to confirm the registration:

Figure 12

3.4.Forest Units Dashboard

The Dashboard is accessible from the top Menu by clicking on “Forest Units.”

3.4.1. Creating New Forest Unit

This procedure applies to **USE CASE A and B1** for the SU who are “Forest Managers” and **C** for the “Logging Company” (§2.2.1).

SU can create a new Forest Management Unit by clicking "Create New Forest Unit," as shown in Figure 13 below.

Domain UUID	Country ID	Region ID	Municipality ID	Property ID	Forest Management Unit ID	Estimated Wood Volume	Processing State	Dominant Tree Species	
Vallombrosa	ITALY	TOSCANA	VALLOMBROSA	PRIVATE	590	2500.0	Awaiting Cut Definition	Douglas Fir	
DOMAINUUID	COUNTRY	REGION	MUNICIPALITY	Private	FMU_001	1000.0	Awaiting Pre-Cut Drone Flight	Dominant Tree Species	

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Figure 13

Now, SU must fill in the fields with the Administrative, Qualitative, Quantitative Forest Unit attributes:

- Administrative Attributes:
 - Domain uuid,
 - Country ID,
 - Region ID,
 - Municipality ID,
 - Property ID
 - **Forest Management Unit (FMU) ID,**
 - Forest Management Sub-Unit (FMSU) ID,
 - Forest Certification Scheme ID;

Figure 14

- Qualitative Attributes:
 - Dominant Tree Species;
 - Quality score (from 1 to 3).
- Quantitative Attributes:
 - Area of FMU or FMSU,
 - Area of FMU or FMSU covered by forest,
 - Estimated wood volume,
 - Measured wood volume.

These attributes are a subset of the Attributes described in the DigiMedFor Deliverable D2.1.

SU must also fill in the fields with the Management attributes:

- Processing state: select the applicable state from the dropdown list:

Figure 15

- Cutting order (harvesting, logging order / permit),
- Documentation (Ancillary documents, Flight Documentation, pictures and reports)
- Users: select Users assigned to the FMU from the list,
- KML file (or .JSON file): click "Choose file" to upload the file with the coordinates of the FMU perimeter.

Create Forest Unit

Domain uuid*	<input type="text"/>	Country ID*	<input type="text"/>
Region ID*	<input type="text"/>	Municipality ID*	<input type="text"/>
Property ID*	Private	Forest Management Unit ID*	<input type="text"/>
Forest Management Sub-Unit ID*	<input type="text"/>	Forest Certification Scheme ID*	Not known
Dominat Tree Species*	<input type="text"/>	Processing state*	Awaiting Pre-Cut Drone Flight
Area of Forest Management Unit (FMU) or Sub-Unit (FMSU)[ha]	<input type="text"/>	Area of FMU or FMSU covered by forest[ha]	<input type="text"/>
Estimated Wood Volume[m ³]*	0,0	Measured Wood Volume[m ³]*	0,0
Cutting order	<input type="button" value="Scegli file"/> Nessun file selezionato	Documentation	<input type="button" value="Scegli file"/> Nessun file selezionato <small>Upload PDF documents or photos (JPG, JPEG, PNG). Maximum size: 5MB</small>
Quality score	<input type="text"/>	Kml file	<input type="button" value="Scegli file"/> Nessun file selezionato
<small>Quality score from 1.0 to 3.0</small>		Cutting end date	<input type="text" value="gg/mm/aaaa"/>
Cutting start date	<input type="text" value="gg/mm/aaaa"/>		
Users*	UserName mario.rossi graziano admin		

Figure 16

SU can also draw the forest unit with the interactive map at the bottom of the screen.

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Figure 17

Finally, SU must click the “SAVE” button (Figure 18).

Cutting start date: gg/mm/aaaa

Cutting end date: gg/mm/aaaa

Users*

UserName
mario.rossi
graziano
admin

Save Back

Search for a place or input lat,lon

Figure 18

3.4.2. Creating Forest Unit from a Traceability Report

This Procedure Applies to Use Case B2 (§2.2.1).

After the Registration (§3.3), SU (who is a Sawmill Manager) must not create a Forest unit from scratch, but the system uses the Load of Logs ID requested in the Registration phase to perform a check on the Forest Unit(s) and make the Forest Unit(s) and their tracked elements appear in the Sawmill Manager's account. Such pre-existing information will not be modifiable.

The Sawmill Manager will then only be able to add information on the Sawn Timber and Batch of Sawn Timber, and to upload ancillary documentation and generate the Traceability Report.

3.4.3. Edit Forest Unit

In the Forest Unit Dashboard, the SU, or the U, can Edit the FMU attributes by clicking on the *pencil* icon Figure 19

Forest Units									
Domain UUID	Country ID	Region ID	Municipality ID	Property ID	Forest Management Unit ID	Estimated Wood Volume	Processing State	Dominant Tree Species	
Vallombrosa	ITALY	TOSCANA	VALLOMBROSA	PRIVATE	590	2500.0	Awaiting Cut Definition	Douglas Fir	
DOMAINUUID	COUNTRY	REGION	MUNICIPALITY	Private	FMU_001	1000.0	Awaiting Pre-Cut Drone Flight	Dominant Tree Species	

Figure 19

SU and U can upload new documents and attachments under the fields “Cutting Order” and “Documentation”.

3.4.4. Delete Forest Unit

In the Forest Unit Dashboard, the SU, or the U, can delete the FMU by clicking on the *trash can* icon (Figure 20).

Forest Units

Domain UUID	Country ID	Region ID	Municipality ID	Property ID	Forest Management Unit ID	Estimated Wood Volume	Processing State	Dominant Tree Species	
Vallombrosa	ITALY	TOSCANA	VALLOMBROSA	PRIVATE	590	2500.0	Awaiting Cut Definition	Douglas Fir	
DOMAINUUID	COUNTRY	REGION	MUNICIPALITY	Private	FMU_001	1000.0	Awaiting Pre-Cut Drone Flight	Dominant Tree Species	

Figure 20

3.4.5. Forest Unit Information

In the Forest Unit Dashboard, the SU and the U, can visualize the FMU information by clicking on the *card* icon (Figure 21).

Forest Units

Domain UUID	Country ID	Region ID	Municipality ID	Property ID	Forest Management Unit ID	Estimated Wood Volume	Processing State	Dominant Tree Species	
Vallombrosa	ITALY	TOSCANA	VALLOMBROSA	PRIVATE	590	2500.0	Awaiting Cut Definition	Douglas Fir	
DOMAINUUID	COUNTRY	REGION	MUNICIPALITY	Private	FMU_001	1000.0	Awaiting Pre-Cut Drone Flight	Dominant Tree Species	

Figure 21

The "Forest Unit Information" page shows:

- at the top left, an excerpt of the FMU attributes (Forest Unit Details)
- at the top right, a preview of the visualization on the Map of the position of the Trees with the RFID tags in the FMU
- at the bottom, the compact view of the traceability elements:
 - Trees,
 - Wood Logs,
 - Sawn Timber.

This section is the only one visible to Guest Users.

Forest Unit Information

Forest Unit Details

Domain UUID: Vallombrosa

Estimated Wood Volume: 2500.0 m³

Measured Wood Volume: 0.0 m³

Processing State: AWAITING_CUT_DEFINITION

Trees in the Forest Unit

Tree ID: E2806891200050082855DC8D	▼
Tree ID: E2806891200040082855E4B7	▼
Tree ID: E2806891200040082855D8E7	▼
Tree ID: E2806891200040082855E4B8	▼

Figure 22

Wood Logs in the Forest Unit

Figure 24

3.4.6. Blockchain “synchronization” and Traceability Report

The Gateway autonomously performs the synchronization of the data associated with the FMU on the blockchain service.

This synchronization takes place in parallel for:

- The recording of traceability and quality information associated with the FMU.
- The recording of authenticated traces of the Traceability Box.

Please note that the System performs this synchronization without any action required by the SU.

The "SU" must click on the "Generate Report" icon to generate the "Traceability Report".

Forest Units

Domain UUID	Country ID	Region ID	Municipality ID	Property ID	Forest Management Unit ID	Estimated Wood Volume	Processing State	Dominant Tree Species	
Vallombrosa	ITALY	TOSCANA	VALLOMBROSA	PRIVATE	590	2500.0	Awaiting Cut Definition	Douglas Fir	
DOMAINUUID	COUNTRY	REGION	MUNICIPALITY	Private	FMU_001	1000.0	Awaiting Pre-Cut Drone Flight	Dominant Tree Species	

Figure 25

For other details check §3.8.

3.5. Map visualization

The Map section is accessible from the top Menu by clicking on “Map.”

Figure 26

In the Map section, is possible to visualize flight trajectories for associated FMUs. The Map is navigable and can be extended at full screen.

Figure 27

Map has a “Replay Mode” section, where users can visualize the recorded surveys,

By clicking on “Play”, the playback of selected recorded survey starts.

As shown in Figure 28, SU and U can also “Pause” the video, set the speed, activate or deactivate the tracking mode, and select the map style.

Figure 28

The “Live Mode” section is used to follow in real time the Data Traceability Box installed on the drone operating in the FMU (Figure 29).

Data Traceability Box System

Operation Mode

Replay Mode Live Mode

● Live Tracking

Position Info

Latitude: 43.730245
Longitude: 11.554827
Date: 25/09/2024
Time: 16:22:54

Abbazia di Vallombrosa
Cappella del Faggio Santo
Cappella del Faggio Santo

mapbox © Mapbox © OpenStreetMap. Improve this map © Maxar

Figure 29

3.6.Devices registration

The registration of the devices can be done through the “Devices” section, accessible from the Top Menu (Figure 30).

Figure 30

This step is necessary for the initial association of the device with the account and its subsequent visibility in the Traceability Report.

The Devices are:

- CAEN RFID skid Reader (§4),
- HITMAN HM220 (§4),
- Traceability Box (§5).

To properly register the devices, please follow these steps:

1. Connect to the DigiMedFor Device Gateway,
2. Log in,
3. from the top menu, select "DEVICES" to register the device,
4. Select among:
 - CAEN RFID skid Reader,
 - HITMAN HM220,
 - Traceability Box.

Register a new device to your account:

Select the device type*

Figure 31

5. Enter the serial number of the device (Figure 32: example of the Traceability Box, Serial Number is on the label on the back of the device)

Figure 32

In the case of the Traceability Box registration, it is needed to indicate the drone model that will be used for the inspection.

3.7. Workflow for data registration

Types of information are described in §2.2.4.

The registration of data with the Android app is described in §4.

Considering the baseline Use case (§2.2.1), SU and U can refer to the following workflows in Table 3:

Workflow 1 – Baseline (Use case A and C)	
1	Create the FMU
2	Register with the Android App the RFID Tags associated with the Trees
3	During the harvesting campaign, register the RFID Tags associated with the Wood Logs and
4	Register with the Android App the Quality measurements taken with the HM220
5	Register with the Android App the RFID tags associated with the Sawn Timber
6	Register the Batch of Sawn Timber
Workflow 2 - Use case A and C	
1	Create the FMU
2	Register with the Android App the RFID Tags associated with the Trees
3	During the Harvesting campaign, register the RFID Tags associated with the Wood Logs and
4	Register with the Android App the Quality measurements taken with the HM220
5	Register with the Android App directly the Batch of Sawn Timber
Workflow 3 – USE CASE B1	
1	Create the FMU
2	Register with the Android App the RFID Tags associated with the Trees
3	During the Harvesting campaign, register the RFID Tags associated with the Wood Logs and
4	Register with the Android App the Quality measurements taken with the HM220
5	Create the Load of Logs with the Android App
Workflow 4 – Sawmill (Use case B2)	
1	Fill-in the User Registration form
2	To “Create Forest Unit from Traceability Report”, add in the User Registration form the ID of the Load of Logs
3	The system will synchronize FMU ID and attributes, and the list of Wood Logs from the Load of Logs
4	Register with the Android App the RFID tags associated with the Sawn Timber
5	Register the Batch of Sawn Timber

Table 3

3.8. Generate the Traceability Report

The Traceability Report is an accompanying document that is generated by the SU for two main reasons:

- accompanying the trade documentation, in this case it is intended for the Customer;
- providing summary information on the implementation of traceability, this document is intended for auditors of competent authorities or other relevant third parties.

The report consists of two parts:

1. Traceability Data of Timber Production
2. Certified Flight Trajectories

Each of the two parts is associated with a QR Code that allows the recipient of the Report to Log in as Guest User and respectively:

- View-Only Forest Unit Information section and view the blockchain record of the information of the Forest Unit of interest.
- View-Only the flight information on the blockchain record for the Forest Unit of interest.

After accessing to the Report Generation (please follow the steps described in §3.4.6).

The Report contains the following sections:

- **Introduction:** which explains the division into two parts and contains the respective QR codes
- **Responsibilities:** which shows information about the person responsible for the Report and the devices used and the Drone Pilot who conducted the surveys
- **Traceability Data:** which shows an excerpt of the Forest Unit Information, which the recipient can compare with what is shown on the blockchain. It also reports:
 - the “. JSON” of the FMU perimeter coordinates,
 - additional data such as harvesting permit, illustrative images, Ancillary documents
- **Certified Flight Trajectory** reports the information on the Traceability box used and on the drone on which it is installed, reports an extract of the view of the flight track executed, which the Recipient can compare with what is shown on the blockchain, and
 - Additional data such as flight report excerpts and relevant photos or flight-related documents (i.e. flight authorization)
- **Remarks:** contain a disclaimer about data responsibility and provides instructions about:
 - How to access the QR codes
 - (for the Sawmill Manager): how to create an account and register as Sawmill by adding the Load of Logs ID

An example of Traceability Report is in §8.

4. Android App

4.1. Description

The primary purpose of the app is to collect data and measurements in the field, which are then sent to the Platform for storing.

It is designed to meet the needs of the following users:

- Forest owners and managers: to manage, qualify, and trace the timber originating from the forest
- Forest logging companies: during harvesting operations, they can tag, trace and qualify round timber
- Sawmills: for tagging, tracing and qualifying the sawn timber they produce.

Figure 33 describes the field workflows for adding elements and qualities to the system in the forest, log yard, or sawmill.

Figure 33

Each item (tree, log, or sawn timber) is tagged using RFID technology, which ensures unique labelling through a code that is both unique and unchangeable. The data related to each item is then linked to this tag, as described in the following sections.

Data related to trees, logs and sawn timber are associated with the forest unit of origin. According to the workflow adopted, they can also be associated with each other, as described in Figure 34.

DATA FLOWS

Figure 34

Figure 35 illustrates the possible workflows for data acquisition, which will be described in detail in the following sections.

APP WORKFLOWS

Figure 35

4.1.1. Mobile device minimum requirements

Mobile device minimum requirements:

- an Android device running Android 11.0 (Pie, API level 31) or later; optimized for Android13 (API level 33).
- The device must support Bluetooth, preferably Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE).

The app uses Google Play Services for geolocation and maps.

4.2. Associated Devices

4.2.1. CAEN RFID skid reader

The **skID (Model R1280IE, R1280IU)** from CAEN RFID³ is a portable RAIN RFID reader of the easy2read© product line with integrated antenna for medium range applications, in particular inventory management for mobile workers.

4.2.2. HITMAN HM220

The **Hitman HM 220** from Fibregen⁴ is an instrument specifically designed for the qualification of round timber.

It measures the natural frequencies of wood as it vibrates freely after being hit. By inputting the length of the examined timber element, the resulting measurement is the velocity of the mechanical wave propagating longitudinally through the wood.

This information is closely related to the wood's mechanical properties and internal defects, and thus to its overall quality.

For additional details refer to Deliverable D3.1 - DigiMedFor tool for in-situ wood evaluation and grading.

³ <https://www.caenrfid.com/it/products/skid-r1280i/>

⁴ <https://www.fibre-gen.com/hitman-hm220>

4.3. User registration and log in

First, a registered user must log in:

Figure 36

4.4. Menu

4.4.1. Pairing

After logging in, the main menu opens.

The first command in the menu allows users to pair devices used for reading RFID tags (RFID reader) and measuring log quality (Hitman HM 220).

These devices must be switched on and connected via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) (Figure 37 and Figure 38).

Figure 37

Figure 38

4.4.1.1. Adding an item

To add an item to the system (whatever the type), User must first tag it with an RFID tag. Once tagged follow these steps (Figure 39):

1. Tap the ADD button – this opens the RFID DETECTION screen.
2. Tap SHORT DETECTION.
3. When the tag is detected, it will appear on the screen. Tap on it.
4. The ADD DETECTION screen opens, displaying the following information (Figure 40):
 - TID code – a permanent, unchangeable identifier
 - EPC code – this can be modified if a custom code is needed. To do so, enter the new number and tap the CHANGE EPC button.
 - Coordinates – the geographical location of the item's origin (e.g., where the tree stands or where the log was cut).
 - Species – this can also be edited by selecting from the drop-down menu.
 - Map – shows the location where the tag was read.
 - Add Item Button – allows you to finalize and save the item in the system.
5. Tap the Add button at the bottom of the screen to add the item to the system.

Figure 39

Figure 40

4.4.2. Forest Unit

By selecting the “Forest Unit” command, the app displays a list of forest units associated with the logged-in user.

To start adding items to a specific unit, it must first be selected.

Once selected, three workflows become available, allowing the user to add:

- Standing trees
- Logs
- Sawn timber items

The final option in the menu is “Synchronize”, which is used to send the data collected via the mobile app to the Traceability Platform (Figure 41).

Figure 41

4.4.2.1. Standing trees

If the harvested trees are marked with RFID tags, they can be linked to the corresponding forest unit, and the resulting logs can be associated with the original trees.

Follow these steps to do so (Figure 42):

1. Select the relevant forest unit. The SINGLE FOREST UNIT MANAGEMENT screen will open.
2. Tap STANDING TREE.
3. Tap the ADD TREE button, then follow the procedure described in section 4.4.1.1 *Adding an item*.

Figure 42

Once a tree is registered in the system, it becomes possible to add a note or observation (NOTE), to add measurements related to the tree (height and diameter, Figure 42 right) if desired, and add the logs cut from it. To do so, follow these steps (Figure 43):

4. Tap the ADD WOOD LOG button, then follow the procedure described in section 4.2.1.1. *Adding an item.*
5. Select the SECTION of the log (e.g. The butt log is section 1, and so forth).

Repeat steps 4 and 5 to add additional logs and link them to the same tree.

By selecting the tag of a log, it is also possible to add annotations using the NOTE button.

This procedure can be repeated for each log and then continued with the next harvested tree.

Figure 43

If the user wants to add measurements (dimensions and wave velocity) to the log immediately after it has been entered, the following procedure applies (Figure 44 and Figure 45):

6. Tap on the tag of the log.
7. Tap on ADD WOOD LOG MEASUREMENT button.
8. Enter the length of the log, then tap SET WOODLOG LENGTH ON INSTRUMENT to send this value to the Hitman HM 220. (Note. The instrument must be paired beforehand).
9. Hit the log and measure the wave velocity using the HM 220.
10. Tap USE STIFFNESS INSTRUMENT to retrieve the velocity measurement into the app.
11. Enter the log diameter (Both end diameters, just one, or none if it is not of interest, can be input).
12. Tap ADD MEASUREMENT to save the data.

Measurements can also be added to logs later, for example, at the log yard.

By following the procedure in steps 4 to 5 to add a wood log, if the log is already present in the system, the ADD MEASUREMENT screen opens. In that case, proceed with steps 8 to 12 as previously described.

Figure 44

Figure 45

4.4.2.2. Wood log

If trees are not tagged within the forest units and the workflow begins directly with wood logs, follow this procedure (Figure 46):

1. Select the forest unit.
2. Tap on the WOOD LOGS button in the menu that appears.
3. To add logs without measurements, tap ADD WOOD LOG button and follow steps 4 to 5 previously described in the section 4.4.2.1 *Standing trees*. If the user wants to perform measurements at this stage, proceed until step 12.

Figure 46

4.4.2.3. Sawn timber

Sawn timber can be added directly to the forest unit without being associated with a specific trees or logs. To do so, follow this procedure (Figure 47):

1. Select the forest unit.
2. Tap the SAWN TIMBER button in the menu that appears.
3. Tap the button ADD SAWN TIMBER and follow the procedure described in section 4.4.1.1 *Adding an item*.
4. If the user wishes to add measurements for the sawn timber, tap the ADD SAWN

- TIMBER MEASUREMENT button. Otherwise repeat step 3 to add more items.
5. Enter the sawn timber dimensions, number of pieces, and quality grade.

Sawn timber can be added as either individual pieces or as a batch, depending on how the labels are applied.

If a single label is used for the entire batch, the batch must be internally homogeneous, meaning all pieces must have the same dimensions and quality grade.

By selecting the tag of a sawn timber, it is also possible to add annotations using the NOTE button.

Measurements can also be added to sawn timber at a later time.

By following the procedure in steps 3 to 4 to add a sawn timber, if the sawn timber is already present in the system, the ADD SAWN TIMBER MEASUREMENT screen opens. In that case, proceed with steps 5 as previously described.

Figure 47

4.4.3. Load of Logs

When logs are loaded for transport to a customer, they can be grouped into a *Load of Logs* to create a record of the shipped material.

To do so, proceed as follows:

1. Select LOAD OF LOGS from the main menu. The ADD LOAD OF LOGS screen will open.
2. Tap the ADD LOAD OF LOGS button.
3. The ADD LOAD OF LOGS screen will appear, and a unique code for the load will be automatically generated. Enter the descriptive information (name and description), then tap CREATE LOAD OF LOGS button.
4. After being redirected to the LOAD OF LOGS screen, tap on the Load to be populated, then tap ADD WOOD LOG.
5. Add wood logs as described in Section 4.4.1.1. *Adding an item.*

Figure 48

The ID of the load of logs will be used to transfer information about the material to the buyer (see §3.4.2 and §3.8).

4.4.4. Tag Verification

The TAG VERIFICATION command in the main menu allows users to view information already registered for items or to complete the addition of missing data. To use this function (Figure 49):

1. Select TAG VERIFICATION from the main menu.
2. Scan the tag with the DETECTION command (ensure the RFID reader is paired).
3. Tap on the detected tag to access the details.

Figure 49

Once an item is detected, its information is displayed (Figure 50), along with the option to modify the EPC code if a custom coding is desired.

The interface also provides commands to add associated items or measurements.

- When a *tree* is detected, you can add measurements related to the tree, as well as logs cut from it and, after that, the log measurements.
- When a *log* is detected, you can add log measurements (see steps 7 to 12 in the section 4.4.2.1 – *Standing Trees*), as well as associate sawn timber.
- When *sawn timber* is detected, you can add measurements related to the sawn wood.

Figure 50

4.4.5. Log processing

Sawn timber can also be added so to be associated to the log processed and continue the flow of information from the forest unit to the tree, to the log, and finally to the sawn timber.

To do so, RFID tags must be applied to each single sawn timber piece. The procedure involves the following steps (Figure 51 and Figure 52):

1. Select LOG PROCESSING from the main menu.
2. Tap ADD LOG TO PROCESS.
3. Scan the tag of the log to be processed.
4. Once the tag is detected, tap on the tag and two buttons become active: FINISH PROCESSING and GENERATE SAWN TIMBER. To begin adding sawn timber pieces, tap GENERATE SAWN TIMBER.
5. The *sawn timber* screen opens Tap ADD SAWN TIMBER.
6. Scan the RFID tag on the sawn timber piece. It will appear on the screen.
7. Tap the detected tag. The ADD SAWN TIMBER MEASUREMENT button becomes active. Tap it to open the screen where the sawn timber details can be added (length, dimension, and quality class).
8. After entering the measurements, the *sawn timber* screen will return, and another sawn timber piece can be added.

Note: If the user does not wish to enter measurements, simply continue tapping ADD SAWN TIMBER to register additional the sawn pieces to the log without measurements.

9. Once added all sawn timber pieces to the log being processed, remove the log from the temporary processing phase by selecting its tag and tapping FINISH PROCESSING.

Figure 51

Figure 52

4.5. Other features

When adding a new item, if the RFID tag is already registered in the system and associated with a different item type, an error message will appear and the tag cannot be reused (Figure 53).

Figure 53

Finally, across the various workflows, double tapping a registered tag displays its associated information in an overlay (Figure 54).

5. UAS Module – Traceability Box

5.1. Introduction

The Traceability box is a tracking and remote identification device for aircraft systems, which features OSNMA Galileo/EGNOS enabled receiver capable to guarantee the authenticity of the position information at the origin.

The tracking information is cyphered for real-time transmission to the Gateway and permanently stored to a private Blockchain node, unalterable once stored.

In addition, beyond any mechanism to avoid the mechanical alteration, the device features a dedicated chip, usually referred as secure element, tailored to avoid secrets exposure.

The Traceability Box is designed to be easy to install on light and small UAS. The weight is 90 grams with normal battery and 113g with extended battery. It can be mounted with dual lock tape or a specific adapter. Once installed, the device can communicate via a direct interface (USB Type-C cable) and remote interface (cellular network).

The device with extended battery provides up to 5 hours of operating time without recharging. It also features an Inertial Module Unit with Gyroscope, accelerometer, magnetometer and barometer sensors.

5.1.1. Device presentation

On the bottom side there are the power slide switch and USB Type-C connector for charging interface. While on the front hand side, the device has four LED indicators, for which a specific section is dedicated.

On the right-hand side there the Micro SD slot with a dedicated LED and a custom button, used for future updates.

The SMA connector for the external GNSS antenna is placed on the left-hand side.

The top-hand side presents an additional SD card and a service only micro-USB port.

Figure 55 Shows the front, bottom, and left side view of the Box. On the bottom side there are the power switch and USB Type connector for charging and payload interface. While on the front hand side, the device has four LED indicators, described in §5.1.2.

Figure 56 shows the right-hand side view, where is positioned a Micro SD slot with a dedicated LED.

Figure 57 shows the left-hand side view.

Figure 55

Figure 56

For a proper functioning, we recommended to use a MicroSD of 4GB or more formatted in FAT32

Figure 57

5.1.2. Led indicators

Figure 58

STATUS		Flashing Yellow Component Preparation
		Flashing Green Ready to fly
		Alternating flashing Green and Red – Prevailing Green Battery level < 40%
		Alternating Green and Red – Prevailing red Battery level < 30%
		Flashing red Device in sleep – Please recharge
		Solid Red: Data storage error, check SD card

CHARGE Built-in battery charging		Solid Red: Charging Off: Charging complete.
OSNMA Position authentication		Flashing: OSNMA is active
RID Remote Identification		Fast flashing blue: RID is active

Table 4

5.1.3. Charging

The DigiMedFor Traceability Box can be charged via the USB cable in the box from any 5V compatible source, such as a computer's USB port, a powerbank or a smartphone adapter. The light on Charge LED indicates that the device is charging. The same LED will turn off once charging is complete.

Charging via cables with the USB-C connector on both sides is not supported for the moment.

5.2. Traceability Box Specifications

Dimensions (WxHxT)	65x59x35 mm
Weight	113 (extended battery)
Enclosure	Self-extinguishing ABS
Fixing mechanism	CANOPUS 3M Dual Lock SJ3550 CF Extra; mechanical adapters for DJI (opt.)
Degree of protection	IP43
Operating Temperature	-20°C / +50°C
Turning on	Manual (slide switch)
LED Indicators	OSNMA, RID, STATUS, CHARGE
Battery life	Up to 5 hours in continuous transmission
Charging	5V – USB type C connector
Positioning	GPS/GLONASS/GALILEO with OSNMA feature
Data Transmission Frequency	1 Hz (1 sample per second)
Network connection	NB-IoT Built-in SIM and antenna
Inflight identification	Network Remote ID
Reference Standards	EASA 2022/024/R (U-Space); ASTM F3411-22 (Specification for remote ID and tracking)

Inertial Module	Gyroscope, accelerometer, magnetometer, barometer
Cyphering and authentication	Crypto Element Device with Secure Hardware-based Key Storage. Secure element for Authentication and key generation.

Table 5

5.2.1. Mounting the Traceability Box on a drone

To install the device for UAS use the CANOPUS 3M Dual Lock tape in the package. The type has is made up of two parts, the first must be glued on the back of the Certiflight Box while the counterpart must be placed on the drone. Follow these steps:

1. Find the flat surface on the drone for the Dual Lock counterpart.
2. Wipe the surface with an alcohol cloth.
3. Wait a few minutes for the alcohol to evaporate.
4. Remove the film from the coupling piece and stick it on the drone.
5. Wait five minutes, so that the glue adheres.
6. Clip the device to the coupling piece on the drone.
7. Make sure the glue on both sides holds securely by repeatedly removing the device from the drone.

The CANOPUS 3M Dual Lock tape supplied in the package guarantees superior performance compared to traditional Velcro.

Alternatively, for DJI M300 users a dedicated mounting adapter is provided, which uses the screw-holes on the topside of the drone.

Figure 59

Figure 60

5.3. Inflight

For each flight operation, it is recommended to follow these steps:

- Turn on the device.
- Check the battery level as indicated in §5.1.2.
- Wait until all components of the device are ready (Status LED flashing green)
- Conducting the mission
- At the end of the mission, turn off the device.

Check the battery level of the Traceability Box the day before the mission and if necessary, recharge it to 100%

5.3.1. Tracking visualization

In the Map section, you can view the location of active devices, and the information transmitted.

Please refer to §3.5 for live tracking visualization.

Figure 61

In particular, the User can visualize:

- Device ID
- UTC Time
- Number of satellites in use
- Number of Authenticated Galileo Satellites
- Battery status
- Cellular signal strength
- Ground speed.
- Ground heading.

6. Final Remarks

This document (D3.2) describes the first version of the Data Traceability Platform System. D3.6 will provide a description of the final version of the system.

As part of the DigiMedFor project wider framework, the Gateway Homepage introduces the DKP (DigiMedFor Knowledge Platform) and provides the link (<https://dkp.cesefor.xyz/>) to allow Users to obtain desired optimal forest pathway, while also obtaining access to a complete repository of forestry datasets and investigation.

6.1. Further developments

One of the further developments identified, which will be included in the final version of the system, is the integration with the TRESTIMA app. This will allow the Super User to create the Forest Unit by uploading a file (.JSON) exported from the TRESTIMA app with the main FMU attributes.

The DTSPS in this first version allows users to indicate the certification scheme that may be adopted in forest management. Based on user feedback during the pilot, more interactions can be set up to support the demonstration of compliance with specific requirements of certification schemes.

The final version of the platform will provide the possibility of selecting the language between English and Italian.

7. References

References from DigiMedFor Project:

- Deliverables:
 - D2.1 - Report on DigiMedFor forest data: used as input for Forest Units Attributes design.
 - D2.2-Toolkit for Forest Managers.
 - D3.1 - DigiMedFor tool for in-situ wood evaluation and grading.
 - D6.6 - Regulatory framework.
- Project website
 - <https://digimedfor.eu/>
 - (Page of the DigiMedFor Project describing the traceability technologies, including the illustrative video: <https://digimedfor.eu/2025/05/28/new-video-explore-digimedfors-wood-traceability-technologies/>)
- Zenodo repository:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/digimedfor/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>
- DigiMedForKnowledge platform: <https://dkp.cesefor.xyz/>

External references

- EU Regulation
 - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02023R1115-20241226>
- Relevant web sites
 - <https://www.caenrfid.com/it/products/skid-r1280i/>
 - <https://www.fibre-gen.com/hitman-hm220>
 - <https://www.rivistasherwood.it/t/lavoro-in-bosco/tavole-sinottiche-obblighi-eudr.html?highlight=WyJtYXJpYW5vliwidGF2b2xlliwixHUyMDFjdGF2b2xlliwidGF2b2xldHRlliwic2lub3R0aWN0ZSJd>
 - https://green-forum.ec.europa.eu/deforestation-regulation-implementation/eudr-cooperation-and-partnerships/country-classification-list_en

8. Appendix – Traceability Report Example

DMF_TRAC_REP_0001
Date of generation
28/05/2025
Page 1

DigiMedFor
Digital Mediterranean Forest

Traceability Report

Report ID: 0001

Date of activity:

Start: 01/09/2024

End: 28/05/2025

FMU Manager: Michela Nocetti

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- 1. Introduction**
- 2. Responsibilities**
- 3. Traceability Data**
- 4. Certified Trajectories**
- 5. Remarks**

1. Introduction

The DigiMedFor Traceability platform offers a digital service for the generation of certified traceability reports of Forest Management Units, comprehensive Traceability Data of the timber production and flight trajectories and the flight logs of Drones.

This document represents the Traceability Report, providing both Traceability of Timber Production and Flight trajectories based on real-time in-flight services data transmitted by the DigiMedFor Traceability Box Device.

This Report can be generated only by the **Forest Manager**, within the Traceability Portal.

Traceability Data of Timber Production

For each Forest Management Unit, traceability data are based on a system of RFID tags attached to the following classes:

- Trees
- Wood Logs
- Sawn Timbers

Reading of RFID tags is done with the device R1280I skid.

Grading information is measured with the device HM220.

Other information is added manually under the responsibility of the Forest Manager.

Flight Trajectories

The core of the system is a Device featuring Galileo OSNMA to guarantee the authenticity of position information at the origin, without the possibility to be counterfeited or spoofed.

Tracking information is encrypted (standard ISO 23629-9) and once transmitted to the Traceability Portal is permanently stored by automation software to an unalterable blockchain private node.

This data includes positioning, time, navigation parameters and telemetry. Basic statistics calculated in post flight are included in this report.

**This Traceability Report refers to the Load of Logs with ID:
14b6d34e-d7d9-405e-b9ea-3ac4859ae13e**

To verify the data of this report, scan the following QR Codes

Timber Traceability Dataset Id:

Flight Trajectories Dataset Id:

2. Responsibilities

This section identifies the responsibilities for the activity executed on the Forest Management Unit identified with **ID 590** from 01/09/2024 to 28/05/2025.

The following information has been provided by user Mario Rossi: DigiMedFor is not responsible for the data in this report.

DigiMedFor is not responsible for the accuracy of the data in this report.

Responsible of the Report

Id	Last Name	First Name	ID Card Passport	Email	Organization	Forest Management Unit ID
0000	Nocetti	Michela	IDCARDNR	michela.nocetti@cnr.it	CNR	590

The Responsible:

- IS the "Operator" according to the [Definitions of the EUDR](#).
- IS NOT the "Operator" according to the [Definitions of the EUDR](#).

Timber Traceability Device

Name	Type	Connectivity	Serial Number	User associated
R1280I skID	RFDI TAG Reader	Bluetooth		Michela Nocetti
HM220	Stiffness measurement	Bluetooth		Michela Nocetti

3. Traceability Data

This section reports an excerpt of the Traceability data included in the Forest Units dashboard section.

The following picture represents an overview of the geolocation of the trees from the FMU.

The main information about the Forest Management Unit are:

Domain UUID: Vallombrosa

Estimated Wood Volume: 2500.0 m³

Measured Wood Volume: 0.0 m³

Processing State: AWAITING_CUT_DEFINITION

Forest Certification : PEFC

Dominant Tree Species: Douglas Fir

This is a sample of Trees in the Forest Unit, listed by unique ID

Tree ID	First Reading Time	Coordinates	Tree Type
E2806891200050082855DC8D	2025-01-14T12:59:37.605000Z	(43.7325755, 11.5563542)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855E4B7	2025-01-17T09:42:32.979119Z	(43.729815, 11.5546719)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855D8E7	2025-01-15T10:30:45.990000Z	(43.7294669, 11.5548985)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855E4B8	2025-01-17T10:17:34.365055Z	(43.7295805, 11.5549812)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855D8E8	2025-01-14T10:44:02.963726Z	(43.729666, 11.5551697)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855F8C7	2025-01-15T08:16:04.706000Z	(43.7297963, 11.5552178)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855D8F6	2025-01-17T09:33:24.345783Z	(43.7298323, 11.5546021)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200050082855B125	2025-01-29T09:26:23.791912Z	(43.6935655, 11.4206076)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855D4B8	2025-01-17T09:08:25.966952Z	(43.7294816, 11.5548648)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855E111	2025-01-14T13:21:00.385000Z	(43.7299141, 11.5551564)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200050082854FCB4	2025-01-22T10:43:50.346940Z	(43.7337202, 11.5580222)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200050082854FD45	2025-01-20T09:18:24.815503Z	(43.7341141, 11.5512714)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E280689120005008285600C7	2025-01-20T09:06:36.633923Z	(43.7337202, 11.5580222)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200050082855B8AB	2025-01-22T07:59:01.716049Z	(43.7337202, 11.5580222)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200050082855E918	2025-01-17T10:34:06.506961Z	(43.7297483, 11.55486)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E280689120005008285604BB	2025-01-20T10:50:22.588487Z	(43.7325693, 11.5548244)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200050082855F0E6	2025-01-15T13:33:01.551000Z	(43.7288195, 11.5369812)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200040082855D4EB	2025-01-22T07:52:58.750163Z	(43.7337202, 11.5580222)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200050082855DCDD	2025-01-15T13:16:12.047000Z	(43.7288195, 11.5369812)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir
E2806891200050082855E8D0	2025-01-22T09:18:58.324504Z	(43.7325693, 11.5548244)	Fir - Italian Tuscany Douglas Fir

This is a sample of Wood Logs in the Forest Unit, listed by unique ID

Wood Log ID	First Reading Time	Tree ID	Log Section Number	Observations
E280689120 000000618C 2433	2025-01-29T 09:14:11.875 628Z	E280689120 0040082855 D504	2	Diameter 1: 29 cm Time of publication: 2025-02-18T10:07:51.967291Z Diameter 2: 31 cm Time of publication: 2025-02-18T10:07:51.967806Z Length : 4.21 m Time of publication: 2025-02-18T10:07:51.968043Z Stiffness : 4.539 Km/s Time of publication: 2025-02-18T10:07:51.968207Z
E280689120 000000618B 80F7	2025-01-17T 09:08:50.649 238Z	E280689120 0040082855 D4B8	1	Diameter 1: 50 cm Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:04:03.378919Z Diameter 2: 40 cm Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:04:03.378991Z Length : 4.19 m Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:04:03.379087Z Stiffness : 4.29 Km/s Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:04:03.379150Z
E280689120 000000618B 90C5	2025-01-20T 10:43:49.547 219Z	E280689120 0050082855 D503	2	Diameter 1: 31 cm Time of publication: 2025-04-11T10:21:33.631145Z Diameter 2: 28 cm Time of publication: 2025-04-11T10:21:33.631212Z Length : 4.19 m Time of publication: 2025-04-11T10:21:33.631268Z Stiffness : 4.44 Km/s Time of publication: 2025-04-11T10:21:33.631316Z
E280689120 000000618B D260	2025-01-20T 10:52:49.097 662Z	E280689120 0050082856 04BB	2	Diameter 1: 32 cm Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:50:20.065357Z Diameter 2: 29 cm Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:50:20.065432Z Length : 4.20 m Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:50:20.065493Z Stiffness : 4.45 Km/s Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:50:20.065546Z
E280689120 0050082855 D917	2025-01-29T 09:26:47.175 171Z	E280689120 0050082855 B125	1	Diameter 1: 35 cm Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:26:39.472471Z Diameter 2: 28 cm Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:26:39.472549Z Length : 4.24 m Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:26:39.472617Z Stiffness : 4.25 Km/s Time of publication: 2025-04-11T09:26:39.472694Z
E280689120 000000618B 2FD8	2025-01-29T 09:02:43.015 694Z	E280689120 0040082855 D4BE	1	Diameter 1: 31 cm Time of publication: 2025-02-18T10:21:38.612305Z Diameter 2: 24 cm Time of publication: 2025-02-18T10:21:38.612675Z Length : 4.23 m Time of publication: 2025-02-18T10:21:38.613046Z Stiffness : 4.402 Km/s Time of publication: 2025-02-18T10:21:38.613353Z

FMU Coordinates

The Coordinated of the FMU are reported below.
The text can be exported as .JSON.

```
{
  "type": "FeatureCollection",
  "features": [
    {
      "type": "Feature",
      "geometry": {
        "type": "Polygon",
        "coordinates": [
          [
            [
              11.553554,
              43.73034
            ],
            [
              11.553756,
              43.730401
            ],
            [
              11.554867,
              43.730268
            ],
            [
              11.555589,
              43.729958
            ],
            [
              11.555194,
              43.729621
            ],
            [
              11.554735,
              43.729325
            ],
            [
              11.554547,
              43.729195
            ],
            [
              11.554371,
              43.729112
            ],
            [
              11.554214,
              43.728927
            ],
            [
              11.554063,
              43.728867
            ],
            [
              11.554132,
              43.729004
            ],
            [
              11.554131,
              43.729073
            ],
            [
              11.55401,
              43.729264
            ],
            [
              11.554016,
              43.729328
            ],
            [
              11.553875,
              43.729555
            ],
            [
              11.553893,
              43.729734
            ],
            [
              11.553554,
              43.73034
            ]
          ]
        ]
      },
      "properties": {}
    }
  ]
}
```


3.1 Additional Data

This section shows the additional data uploaded by the Forest Manager and referring to the activity executed on the Forest Management Unit identified with **ID 590** from 01/09/2024 to 28/05/2025.

4. Certified Trajectories

This section shows the certified flight trajectory of the activity of Pre-cut drone flight executed on 25/09/2024

The reported activity started at 25/09/2024 16:21:28 and ended at 25/09/2024 16:40:21.

Traceability Box Device

Name	Type	SIM	Serial Number	Aircraft Associated	PK
Traceability box 1	Traceability Box	8988228066 6020772053	pFdQ3vXmj1	DJI M300 RTK TopView	B68C19B16B60D8DE0F25DE7 D84EF9ACE19B349D4C8FDB0 704C201D5451AA8238FF2FFC 58CA43CEC8D

Aircraft

Type	Model Name	MTOM	UAS Serial Number
Drone	DJI M300 RTK Topview	9,0	1ZNDH8500BBMWY

The position records that compose this flight trajectory are stored in blockchain and are exported in a .csv file containing the following columns: time (key): both UTC and epoch time are indicated. This is the key to verify the dataset on the blockchain landing page included in the QR code of this document

- position (lat, lon): as retrieved during real time campaign
- battery (%)
- signal strength (%)

Contract: Pre-cut drone flight LIDAR inspection 25-09-2024 associated to the activity TraceabilityBox1 A024.

File kml selected: Vallombrosa FMU.kml

Compliance Result: OK

4.1 Additional Data

This section shows the additional data uploaded by the Pilot and referable to the activity executed on 25/09/2025.

25/09/2024 16:25
Lat: 43.123456
Lon: 11.123456

25/09/2024 16:30
Lat: 43.123456
Lon: 11.123456

25/09/2024 16:32
Lat: 43.123456
Lon: 11.123456

25/09/2024 16:35
Lat: 43.123456
Lon: 11.123456

5. Remarks

DigiMedFor Data Traceability Platform System has no responsibility on the data filled in this document. If the recipient of the Traceability Report wants to manage the traceability of wood with the DigiMedFor Data Traceability Platform System, they must create their account starting from this [link](#).

In the Registration form, please declare being a recipient of this Traceability Report by entering the ID of the Load of Log present at page 4 of this Report.

